

The metaverse and virtual businesses: A research on the effect of data breaches on stock prices of companies with a virtual presence in the metaverse.

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ABSTRACT

October 2021 the Connect of 2021 took place, in which Mark Zuckerberg, the CEO of then Facebook and current Meta, announced that the Facebook brand will continue under a new name called Meta. Meta's focus is to carry different applications and technologies they manage under this name and to focus on the 'metaverse'. Since this statement by Meta, the interest(s) and searches for the word metaverse have increased by 500%, with Asia and North-America leading the way. This means that the word metaverse has been around for a while, but was not that popular until recently. There are articles that show that in 1995 and 2002 the word was already being used. metaverse is commonly defined as a post-reality universe, perpetual and persistent multiuser environment merging physical reality with digital virtuality. In the physical reality, businesses are the backbone of the economy and these are threatened with all kinds of digital crime, such as cyber crime. Research has shown that cybercrime will only increase in the following years, and with the rise of the metaverse, it will result in increased risks for virtual businesses in losing financial assets. Cybercrime and different attacking methods, such as data leaks, will continue to persist in the metaverse. Digital and cybercrime in the virtual world, looking at virtual businesses, have not yet been researched, specifically on how a data breach in particular can financially impact the stock market of a 'physical' business. This describes the current knowledge gap in this field. Therefore the researchers agreed to explore an

issue that could be of great value to the future of digital technology and conducted research regarding the effects on stock prices of a company after a data breach on virtual businesses in the metaverse.

Keywords: Affect, Company, Confidence, Data breach, Disclosure, Influence, Metaverse, Public, Relationship, Stock Price, Virtual Business

INTRODUCTION

In 2022, the word 'metaverse' has become an integral part of the current world of digital technology. The metaverse is an online virtual world where users can interact with each other in a computer-generated environment of three dimensional objects with user interaction (Dwivedi et al., 2022). It brings many advantages with it and people and businesses around the world start to acknowledge the positive benefits of it , such as gaming, recreation, education and business (Statista, 2022). The metaverse has many different aspects that are parallel to the real world, such as: using digital currency to buy items (e.g. clothing or footwear), play virtual games, socialize with (new) friends, attend concerts and shows, the list goes on. One aspect that is likely to play a major role in the metaverse, as in the real world, is the existence of virtual businesses (Rehm et al., 2015). Virtual businesses within the metaverse are comparable to the exact same businesses in the real world, but virtually. The principle behind the business remains the same. The transition to virtual businesses is naturally accompanied by new types of cyber risks

(Jang-Jaccard & Nepal, 2014). Data breaches that occur for instance, after a ransomware attack, can lead to financial losses for businesses. Businesses that will make use of the metaverse, need to properly secure their (sensitive) data to minimize their risks for data breaches. Since the metaverse and virtual businesses are getting more popular, the associated risks, as described before, will also increase. What could the financial impact, regarding the stock price of a company, be if a data breach happens to the virtual business of that company? The virtual business will endure losses in revenue, such as loss in virtual (crypto) currency, virtual objects, real money, NFT's and/or others. This research will aim to find the answers of these questions. Finally, this study is (socially) relevant for business owners and anyone interested in this topic. It will give more background information on potential new virtual business owners in the metaverse. Furthermore, other researchers and companies can use this research as a backbone for future follow-up research.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The metaverse is a form of digital transformation which increased rapidly in popularity. It conceived new opportunities in the field of gaming, recreation, education and trading. Many businesses in the physical world have been making the transmission into the metaverse, with the main goal to increase its revenue and increase the value of its stock market (Belk & Humayun & Brouard, 2022). But everything has a downside, including this. The transitioning to the digital world also bears the fact that these virtual businesses will more likely be exposed to cybercrime and the associated modus operandi. One of the consequences of this involves the financial losses of a virtual business after a data breach. Research has shown that cybercrime will only increase in the following years, and with the rise of the metaverse, it will result in increased risks for virtual businesses in losing financial assets. Cybercrime and different attacking methods, such as data leaks, will continue to persist in the metaverse, but no research has been done before on how data breach in particular can financially impact the stock market of a 'physical' business. This describes the current knowledge gap in this field. This subject is particularly relevant nowadays since many potential organizations are considering moving into the metaverse, with a risk of being a victim of cybercrime (Belk & Humayun & Brouard, 2022).

RESEARCH QUESTION

The following research question has been formulated for this research: *“How does a data breach on a virtual business in the metaverse affect the stock price of a company?”*

The following four sub-research questions will support the research question:

1. What is the relationship between a company and its stock price?
2. How does a data breach affect a company?
3. What is the influence of a data breach on a stock price of a company?
4. What role does public confidence and disclosure play in a data breach and how does this affect the stock price?

METHODOLOGY

Firstly, this research is investigative and exploratory in nature. A literature review study methodology was used to gain answers on how a data breach on a virtual business in the metaverse affects the stock price of a company. Thus, it is possible to explore in literature what is known or not known about this topic and where there are gaps that can be filled by qualitative methods in a future study. Qualitative designs are more in-depth than quantitative designs, resulting in collecting more data to better understand specific contexts, phenomena or behaviors. The literature review is the first step in finding out the possible effects. For the purpose of validity and reliability, only academic sources from specific databases and journals have been analyzed and chosen. Also, only peer reviewed articles have been taken into account during this research to further improve the quality of this study. Based on the literature review, an analysis has been conducted on the found sources by using the article summary form.

Article Summary Form

Different sources have been used in order to find relevant and useful information. For this study, the following resources have been used, see table 1:

Table 1 - Resources used in order to find relevant information

Databases	Journals
ResearchGate	Journal of the Association for Information Systems (JAIS)
Google Scholar	ScienceDirect
Elsevier	Information Systems Research (ISR)
JSTOR	Journal of Management Information System (JMIS)
	Journal of Information Technology (JIT)

In order to find the most suitable and relevant articles through the resources above, the tracking of key words was necessary to make this research valid and transparent. Be aware that the use of synonyms for the keywords below was occasionally required to find certain articles.

Keywords: Affect, Company, Confidence, Data breach, Disclosure, Influence, metaverse, Public, Relationship, Stock Price, Virtual Business, Relationship data breach and virtual business.

The found papers, journals, articles and researches that were found using the table above, were examined for validity and reliability by using the article summary form that can be seen in Table 2. The table defines the requirements/criteria academic articles must fulfill. The more of the cells of the summary form can be filled in, the more valid and reliable a source is. Naturally, informal sources have been used for non-academic facts and information.

Table 2 - Found articles requirements (Meesters, 2022)

Setting	Bibliography research	Methodology	Subjects	Treatment	(Statistical) research
Geographical	Title	Research design	General characteristics	Dependent variable (Y) and independent variable (X)	Hypothesis accepted or rejected
Institutional	Name author(s)	Operationalisation	Conditions to participate	Treatment	Results
Research objective	Journal impact factor	Time frame	Process of selecting a sample	Hypothesis	Opinion about the treatment
Perspective	Peer review	Procedure	Composition of the sample	Direction hypothesis?	
Context	Year	Validity	Number of respondents	Level of significance	
Does the setting(s) suit the research	Publication in Web of Science	Reliability	Response rate	Opinion about the treatment	

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This explanatory research explains the relationships between variables, called the conceptual model. The visualization can be found in figure 1, shown below. The relationship advertised is between the independent variable 'data breach' and the dependent variable 'stock price'. The goal was to ascertain the connection between the two variables and how they influence each other. So, how does a data breach influence the stock price of a specific company? The moderator variable 'company' and 'public confidence/ disclosure' has its place between the independent variable and the dependent variable, since it can have an influence on the dependent variable 'stock price'.

Figure 1 - Conceptual model

Company

The word 'company' is mentioned many times in this research. But what is the meaning of a company in this research? A company is a legal entity formed by a person or a group of people that sells goods or services to others, with the intention of making profit. In this paper, research has been done regarding a company in the metaverse. This research will argue that a virtual business is part of the same company, which is active in the metaverse, selling digital goods and products, is called a 'virtual business'. Both terms will be used interchangeably during this paper.

A virtual business is any business that conducts all or most of its business via the internet (Ward, 2020) and is part of a 'physical' company. This research investigates specifically at virtual businesses operating within the metaverse selling goods or services with crypto's, NFTs or other virtual currencies. We describe companies with the following relevant characteristics in this research:

- It must consist of multiple employees working on a shared goal
- It is active in the stock market
- It provides services and/or goods in the metaverse, and so, has
- It must have a department specifically for the metaverse and focuses on it as a future goal
- It must trade in virtual currencies, NFT's, physical currencies and/or others

Furthermore, a company, and a virtual business can distinguish itself from competitors by the following factors:

- Organization Structure
- Organization Size
- Budget
- Business Model
- Selling goods and services
- And more.

These factors can influence how a company can react to a data breach in the metaverse. Since this is not the focus of this research, the exact influence

Considering the lack of prior research about this subject, together with the fact that this is relatively new and unknown, it has been decided to not to focus on a specific industry or specific type of business, regarding location size and more. No distinction has been made between the possible (financial) impact of a (virtual) business and its stock price, for the reasons above mentioned.

As mentioned above under the characteristics, is there a difference between a virtual business and a business operated in the physical world. A virtual business in this paper is referred to as a business which operates within the metaverse, which means the business is selling their virtual goods and/or services in context. On the other hand, a business in the physical world differs since it also has physical assets and deals with physical goods and/or services. Furthermore, the clients for the virtual businesses are other players or users within the same virtual world/ metaverse, unlike for the physical businesses, where clients are other businesses or particulars.

Data breaches

Incidents involving data breaches have been rising in recent years and cause serious legal (GDPR), financial and public damage. A data breach is defined as an incident (or breach) where unauthorized access is gained to sensitive, secured and confidential (company) data, which could result in the compromise of the confidentiality, integrity and availability (CIA) of data (Sen & Borle, 2015). Access could be gained, by groups or individuals with malicious intent, using a variety of methods and approaches. Some examples are ransomware (malicious software asking for ransom otherwise it could expose data), malware (malicious software that performs malicious actions) and zero-day attacks (vulnerability used by hackers to exploit and gain access to data or other important information) (Holtfreter & Harrington, 2015). Many prevention methods have been developed to prevent these types of cyberattacks. The purposes of data leak prevention and detection (DLPD) systems are to identify, monitor, and prevent unintentional or deliberate exposure of sensitive information in an enterprise environment. DLPD usually uses the actual content or surrounding context of the monitored data to detect potential leakage (Cheng et al., 2017).

Stock prices

The stock price refers to the current price that a share of stock is trading for on the market (CFI, 2022). The main characteristics of a company should be; listed on the stock exchange and also operational in the metaverse with their virtual business. This could be a possible company to have an eye on regarding the effects on their stock price with occurring cyber-risks. A data breach or a similar incident can have a drastic effect on a stock price, which can then have dramatic consequences for a company.

Public confidence/disclosure

Loss of public confidence or customer confidence can have an impact on the company when it's targeted with a cyberattack. When a data breach occurs and sensitive customer information is leaked this may affect even the stock price of the company, because the breach involves sensitive data (Robinson & Covey, 2022).

RESULTS

What is the relationship between a company and its stock price?

The relationship between a virtual business and stock price can have several aspects. If a company like Nike, starts a virtual business in the metaverse, will it have an effect on its stock price? Nike launched its virtual business in the metaverse by setting up "Nikeland" in the Roblox landscape and selling its NFT collection to interested parties (Bhattacharya, 2022). This earned Nike about \$185 million. But on the contrary, stock prices actually went down 40% in 2022. In any case, this does mean that a virtual business may contain a relationship with stock price, but this relationship should be further investigated by adding multiple variables. Examples of other variables such as Net Profit Margin (NPM) or Debt Equity Ratio (DER) can help explain the relationship between a virtual (and also physical) business and stock price better. Research shows that Net Profit Margin and Debt Equity Ratio has a significant positive effect on Stock price (Sukesti et al., 2021). This means that when the profits of the business increase, the stock price of the business also increases. The same goes for the Debt Equity Ratio, if the debt policy of the company is well designed, then the profits will increase and consequently so will the firm value and/or the stock price of the company.

How does a data breach affect a company?

A data breach can affect a company considerably in various aspects, the most important of which are; Financially, socially and publicly (Chatterjee et al., 2019). From a financial point of view, an organization can have a difficult time as soon as a data breach occurs in which, for example, customer data is published or when certain internal data is encrypted with the help of a data breach. The GDPR will hand out a fine to a company based on the security of customer data (European Union, 2016) and paying ransom for (customer) data will certainly not be free given the malicious intent. Socially wise a company will suffer from the mistrust of consumers, who will worry about their current and future information (Xhafa et al., 2020). A global outrage could even occur, if the company is located worldwide and the data breach has such an impact, where customers cannot access or do anything because the company has taken measures in favor of the company and its safety (D'Arcy et

al., 2020b). Finally, there is the public aspect of a data breach. A company where a data breach has occurred must publicly recover from everyone, such as customers, shareholders and competitors. How can the company restore trust among customers and shareholders, and how can they show competitors that they still belong at the top after an event that can seriously damage a company's reputation if the follow-up and aftercare were not executed properly (Gwebu et al., 2018).

What is the influence of a data breach on a stock price of a company?

That a data breach has an impact on a company as a whole and its business is no new information, but what if the company, a publicly traded and not private one, is also listed on a stock exchange? This means that the company went public for everyone to buy its stock and be a shareholder. A study in which 467 data breach events were investigated at various companies shows the impact this has on a company's stock price differs per type of data breach. The average drop in stock due to a data breach was .37%, but once a data breach occurred due to payment fraud, a company's stock price was expected to drop by 3% (Johnson et al., 2017a). In addition, 96 companies from the S&P 500 have been examined and cross-sectional analysis has shown that there is evidence that on the day of the data breach (day zero) a company's stock price decreases. The stock price of companies in the financial industry fell even more than others (Tweneboah-Koduah et al., 2020). Even companies that have higher growth opportunities, clear evidence shows that not only the stock price of the company itself, but also the stock market as a whole is negatively affected by a data breach (Gatzlaff & McCullough, 2010).

It is striking that the type of company (large, small, sector, etc.) does not necessarily play a major role in the influence of data breach on the stock price. Remarkably enough, when a large company is affected by a data breach, there is a greater chance that a data breach will occur again (several) times than with small companies (Johnson et al., 2017a).

What role does public confidence and disclosure play in a data breach and how does this affect the stock price?

The role of public confidence and disclosure in a data breach play a very important

role, as it has been confirmed from a study by Masuch et al. that if a company apologizes when a data breach has occurred, it will negatively affect the stock price of the company. While withholding this information, which means not disclosing the data breach, generally has no impact on the company's stock price. Unless it later comes to light, it then has an even greater, negative effect than apologizing in advance, or at least disclosing the occurred event (Masuch et al., 2020). There is a difference however, for companies in the financial sector, the stock price decreases faster after disclosure than before disclosure. But the case is very different with companies in other sectors. There is hardly any difference in stock price, before or after disclosing the occurred data breach (Tweneboah-Koduah et al., 2020).

DISCUSSION

In this paper, the researchers present a study that examines the stock price of a company that could be affected by a data breach on a virtual business in the metaverse. The sources used in the study were mainly taken from the journals and databases described in Table 1 and tested as conditions against the appropriate requirements in Table 2. Before the (literature) research, the researchers expected that finding academic sources on the topic of metaverse would be relatively small. Even though writing the theoretical framework was uncomplicated because the terms were simple to describe (in the context of this research), searching for relevant academic studies was a challenging task. Given the use of sources in this research, sufficient papers have been found that are relevant, because the researchers spent an enormous amount of time finding applicable sources by using specific keywords, phrases and sentences.

The results that emerged during the study are half in line with the idea that the researchers had before the study. For example, Tweneboah-Koduah et al. conducted research based on S&P 500 companies, while it would also have been interesting to the researchers that other companies outside the S&P 500 would be examined. Would the result have been the same? The researchers don't know that, unfortunately. On the other hand, because this research focuses on the stock price of a company, sources were mainly sought that focus on

companies that have gone public (have a stock price and therefore sell stock to a stock exchange).

One of the major constraints this study had was the time span of approximately 2.5 months to conduct a research, and the limitation of current studies on this topic. It has become clear to the researchers that no research has ever been done into the main question, or in that direction, as a result of which combining knowledge from sources was necessary ($a+b=c$). The topic regarding virtual businesses within the metaverse in combination with its stock price after a data breach is a fairly new research area in which not much is known. Research has previously been done concerning the metaverse, virtual businesses or the stock price, but none have combined these attributes together so far.

The reader should bear in mind that the study is based on (academic) literature research. In the early stages of the study, the researchers planned to conduct interviews in order to gather information from this day and age to add the opinions and perspectives of the people who specialize in the subject metaverse into the research. Although the researchers had time to arrange interviews within a time span of 2.5, after a month during the initial phase of the research, it turned out that none of the respondents had any time because of the busy season. This forced the researchers to switch from field information to information from literature.

Also, the focus of this study is on companies that are listed on the stock exchange and careful attention must be paid when applying the results to other (research) contexts. A small amount of this research can be generalized and because this is a specific study on a specific subject, the researchers recommend further research that focus on other industries beyond stock exchange listed companies; such as the financial, retail and entertainment sector. The researchers see the financial, retail and entertainment sector as interesting topics for further research, where the focus can be placed on how a data breach can have an impact on the operational functioning of the physical company once it takes place in the virtual (metaverse) world. Finally, it is also interesting to interview companies that want to represent themselves in the metaverse and to include their opinion of the business. The opinions of companies that want to use the metaverse are of

great value to tighten knowledge gaps and help future research(ers) make use of this data, because of a lack of studies on metaverse companies.

CONCLUSION

Based on conducted research, the researchers agree that it is difficult to give a clear conclusion on how a data breach on a virtual business within the metaverse would affect the stock price of a company. Although it can be concluded that the stock price of a company will most likely decrease if a data breach occurs on the virtual business of a company in the metaverse, since the virtual business (in the metaverse) is linked to the ('real-life') company and therefore a data breach causes financial, social and public impact, which then affects the stock price, the researchers are convinced that a clearer and stronger conclusion can be drawn if future research on topics discussed in the discussion chapter will be conducted. The researchers believe that more/future research on the topic and theme of metaverse is important because, as described in the introduction, the term is getting more recognition and is seen as future technology. The world is getting more technical everyday and the metaverse is a part of that, but unfortunately the current knowledge about this subject is still limited.

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